

The Fokker-Planck Equation and Arrangements

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is associated with the maximization of Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln[P(e_i/T)]$ subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$. The entropy form in this case is equivalent to the logarithm of the number of arrangements i.e. $\ln\{ N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \}$ where $n(e_i) = NP(e_i/T)$ if one uses Stirling's approximation. This means that each arrangement carries the same weight which is equivalent to the statement: $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ for allowing all distributions of energy to have equal probability. Thus in the MB case, the notion of maximizing arrangements subject to a constant average E and the idea of entropy $dS/dP = ae$ coincide. In general, however, this is not the case.

$dS/dP = ae$ seems to be the recipe used in the literature (1) i.e. there exists a function of P such that its derivative d/dP yields $a+be$ (energy) which is a physical constraint in the problem (average energy is actually used). This, however, need not be linked to equally weighted arrangements because $P(e_i)P(e_j)=P(e_i+e_j)$ does not always hold. For example, it does not hold for a power law $C(1-ke/T)$ (power $1/k$), but entropy may still be created using $dS/dP = 1-ke/T$. Furthermore one may consider arrangements and maximize them as well to obtain the same power law distribution, but the constraint is no longer $\sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$. The constraint is $\sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(P(e_i/T))$ which in the MB case yields average energy.

In this note, we argue that the Fokker-Planck equation leads to the arrangement maximization form (i.e. d/dP or a Shannon's entropy) with the special constraint needed being linked to the diffusion coefficient.

Entropy and Equally Weighted Arrangements

We argue that entropy is based on the following recipe:

- (A) $P(e_i/T)$ may be solved for e_i/T i.e. $e/T = \text{Function}(P)$. In some cases one has $a+be_i/T$ and so one solves for this.
- (B) One integrates $\text{Function}(P)$ with respect to dP so that d/dP returns e_i/T or $a+be_i/T$. Average energy is considered to be a physical constraint in the problem and entropy is linked to it.

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, the entropy is Shannon's entropy: $-\sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(P(e_i/T))$. The MB case is also equivalent to:

$$P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j) \quad ((1))$$

Thus the idea of conservation of energy is not just a global constraint, but appears in a product of probabilities expression. This is important because it means that given a total energy E , it may be distributed among N particles in any manner such that each arrangement carries the same weight. Thus, one may maximize the \ln of the total number of arrangements subject to the

average energy constraint. To see this more explicitly, one may consider the \ln of the number of arrangements:

$$\ln \left\{ \frac{N!}{\prod_i n_i(e_i/T)} \right\} \text{ where } n_i(e_i/T) = N P_i(e_i/T) \quad ((2))$$

Using Stirling's approximation for large N : $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N)$ leads to:

$$\ln(\text{arrangements}) = \text{constant} - \sum_i n_i(e_i/T) \ln(n_i(e_i/T)) \quad ((3))$$

Thus in the MB case, Shannon's entropy appears from the $dS/dP = e_i/T$ recipe and from the \ln of the number of arrangements. These two approaches coincide, but this is not always the case. For example, it does not hold for a Power Law distribution.

Power Law Distribution, Entropy and $\ln(\text{Arrangements})$

In (2), a power law distribution is given as:

$$P(e_i/T) = C (1 - ke/T)^{1/k} \quad ((4))$$

The entropy recipe $dS/dP = 1 - ke/T$ may be applied to this problem. This means that the constraint is: $\sum_i P(e_i/T) (1 - ke/T)$ which is linked to average energy and $\sum_i P(e_i) = 1$. Thus entropy is linked to the physical notion of conserved energy. In this case, however,

$$P(e_i)P(e_j) \neq P(e_i + e_j) \quad ((5))$$

In other words, one cannot distribute energy in all possible ways and have equal probabilities. Nevertheless, one may create equal weighted arrangements, but the constraint $\sum_i P(e_i/T)$ cannot be used. A different conservation of probability constraint is needed. Using ((4)) and taking \ln of ((5)) one sees that:

$$\ln(1 - ke_i/T) \ln(1 - ke_j/T) = \ln(1 - ke_{i+j}/T) \quad ((6))$$

Thus $\sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(1 - ke_i/T)$ is the constraint to use with arrangements. In such a case, one may use Shannon's entropy again. One may note that in information theory $\ln(P)$ is called information, but it is also directly linked to the number of arrangements through Stirling's approximation.

As a result, the power law distribution may be obtained from two different maximization recipes, each one maximizing a different quantity and using a different constraint.

$$((A)) \quad dS/dP = 1 - ke/T$$

$$((B)) \quad \text{extremization of } -\sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(P) + b \sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(1 - ke_i/T)$$

One approach is concerned with the total average energy ((A)), while the other with equally weighted arrangements.

Fokker-Planck Equation and Arrangements

We next consider the Zwanzig form of the Fokker-Planck equation given in (2):

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial density}(x,p,t) = -p/m \frac{d \text{density}}{dx} \text{partial} + \frac{d}{dp}(\text{partial}) \{ \frac{dV}{dx} + g(x,p)p \} \text{density} + \frac{d}{dp} \text{partial} D \frac{d}{dp} \text{partial} \text{density} \quad ((7a))$$

Here density= P(ei/T). Given that: -p/m dP/dx cancels dV/d dP/dx:

$$\frac{d}{dp} (\text{partial}) \{ g(x,p)pP + D \frac{d}{dp} \text{partial} P \} = 0 \quad ((7b)) \quad \text{for} \quad \frac{dP}{dt} \text{partial} = 0$$

This implies that the quantity in {} is a constant. Setting this constant to 0 yields and using g(x,p)=constant for simplicity yields:

$$gP - Dk/m \frac{d}{dy} P = 0 \quad \text{where} \quad y=1-kei/T \quad \text{and} \quad ei= V(x) + pp/2m \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Then:} \quad \frac{d}{dy} \ln(P) = gm/(kD) \quad \text{or:} \quad \ln(P) = \text{Integral} \frac{dm}{(kD)} dy \quad ((9))$$

ln(P) is information in information theory, but is also associated with a count of the number of equally weighted arrangements through Stirling's approximation. Integral dm/D dy yields the constraint associated with equally weighted arrangements. Let us consider the MB and Power Law cases.

In the MB case: ln(P) = y i.e. e/T (unnormalized P) so D must be a constant. Thus constant*e is used in the constraint associated with arrangements. This, however, yields the average energy constraint: Sum over i ei P(ei/T). Thus maximizing the number of arrangements with respect to average energy yields the MB result.

In the Power Law Case, ln(P) = 1/k ln(1-ek/T) (unnormalized P). Thus D = constant(1-ke/T). D from the Fokker-Planck equation plays a key role in determining the constraint function involving energy which allows for equally weighted arrangements.

The Fokker-Planck equation is often not written in the Zwanzig form ((7a)), but rather in the form:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} P = -\frac{d}{dp} (u(x,p)P) + \frac{d}{dp} \frac{d}{dp} \{ D^2(x,p) P(x,p) \} \quad ((10))$$

Here D²(x,p) is called the diffusion coefficient and u(x,p) the drift. If one uses: u(x,p) = g(x,p)p and considers for simplicity g(x,p)=constant, then:

$gP + dD^2/dp P + D^2 dP/dp = \text{constant}$ ((11)) Taking constant=0 and $g=1$, yields:

$$k/m \frac{d}{dy} \ln(P) = (1-k/m \frac{dD^2}{dy}) / D^2 \quad ((11))$$

For the MB case, D^2 is still a constant. For the Power Law case, one may use $D = \text{constant} * D^2 = b(1-ke/T)$ where $y = (1-ke/T)$ so that $dD^2/dy = \text{constant}$.

Thus the diffusion coefficient again defines the constraint which is involved with equally weighted arrangements.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that there are two maximization recipes associated with a probability distribution, but each potentially uses a different constraint and maximizes a different quantity. The first is entropy: $dS/dP = a + be_i/T$ which is linked with an average energy constraint, S being maximized. The second approach is to maximize the \ln of the number of equally weighted arrangements using $\ln(N! / \text{Product } n(e_i/T)!)$ and Stirling's approximation $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N)$. This leads to the maximization of a Shannon's type entropy $-\sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(P)$ subject to some constraint associated with $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_k)$ i.e. $\sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P)$.

In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, the two approaches coincide. $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2)$ so a constraint associated with equally weighted arrangements is: $\sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$. This is the average energy. Thus entropy and $-P \ln(P)$ coincide.

In other situations, such as in the case of a power law distribution: $P(e/T) = C(1-ke/T)^{1/k}$, $P(e_i)P(e_j) \neq P(e_i+e_j)$ so the constraint associated with \ln of equally weighted arrangements is not average e . Instead it is: $\ln(P(e_i)) + \ln(P(e_j)) = \ln(P(e_k))$ or: $\sum_i P(e_i/T) \ln(1-ke_i/T)$ is the constraint.

We argue that the Fokker-Planck equation may be recast into a maximization of \ln of equally weighted arrangements with the diffusion coefficient helping to define the appropriate constraint.

References

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